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"Perfect" markers for the semidwarfing gene *sd1* in rice

M.H. Ellis and W. Spielmeier, CSIRO Plant Industry, GPO Box 1600, Canberra ACT 2601, Australia
E-mail: marc.ellis@csiro.au

The semidwarfing *sd1* gene, the most common height-reducing gene in rice, is present in most modern cultivars. It was introduced into indica rice varieties in the 1960s with IR8, the cornerstone of the Green Revolution. Independently, a different *sd1* allele was identified in a japonica background following mutagenesis (Mackill and Rutger 1979).

The presence of *sd1* can be determined only from the final height of the plant, which is scored late in development, and is influenced by environmental factors. Furthermore, *sd1* is a recessive gene, and heterozygosity at the *sd1* locus can be determined only by progeny testing. The development of a molecular marker for *sd1* would therefore provide breeders with additional options to test for the presence of short or tall alleles rapidly and at any growth stage.

The gene encoding *sd1* has recently been cloned (Monna et al 2002, Spielmeier et al 2002). The semidwarf stature is due to a genetic mutation in a gene involved in the production of the growth hormone gibberellin (*Os200x2*). Using the *Os200x2* gene sequence, we combined polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and restriction digestion of PCR products to produce specific markers for the two major semidwarf and tall alleles of *sd1*.

PCR was set up in a total volume of 20 mL and contained 100 ng of template DNA, 2 mL Hotstar buffer (Qiagen), 4 mL Q solution, 0.4 mL 10 mM dNTP, 2 mL 10 mM Sd1-F primer, 2 mL 10 mM Sd1-R primer, and 0.2 mL

Hotstar Taq. The primers used were

Sd1-F: 5'- CAC GCA CGG GTT CTT CCA GGT G-3'

Sd1-R: 5'- AGG AGA ATA GGA GAT GGT TTA CC-3'

The cycling conditions were 94 °C, 5 min; five cycles (at 94 °C, 30 s; 55 °C, 30 s, and 72 °C, 1 min 30 s), 30 cycles (at 94 °C, 20 s; 55 °C, 20 s, 72 °C, 1 min); and 25 °C, 1 min.

To determine the Calrose 76 allele, 2 mL of digestion enzyme *Xho*I was added to the PCR prod-

ucts and the mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. The PCR and digestion products were separated by agarose gel electrophoresis and visualized after ethidium bromide staining using standard protocols.

The *sd1* allele present in indica rice (originating from Dege-wo-gen [DGWG]) was found to contain a 383-bp deletion in the genomic sequence of *Os200x2* (Monna et al 2002, Spielmeier et al 2002). We designed PCR primers that spanned

